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EDUCATION MANAGEMENT AS A TOOL FOR STUDENT CHARACTER BUILDING: A SOCIOLOGY OF EDUCATION PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: Character education is education aimed at improving the quality and outcome of education that leads to the improvement of a person's potential, talent, abilities through a systematic process in the human form of character. This article aims to explain how sociological science plays a role in building and familiarizing the character of the introverted pupils. Educational sociology is the social science that studies facts, norms, and social deviations, which are key factors in the process of character formation. This research uses a qualitative approach with research methods of library study and research data from sources of literature, journals, and books. In this method, all the data obtained will be analyzed to draw conclusions. The results of this study show that the sociology of education as a branch of the sciences of sociology played an important role in the formation and cultivation of the character of the students who are integrated in the school.

Keywords: Sociology of Education; Character; Learners; Education Management.

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Introduction

The change in the social order of life of Europeans in the early 20th century caused the benefits of sociology to become crucial in accompanying the educational process in Europe. These developments are the effects of social revolution in different parts of Europe [1]. Since mankind was born to the world consciously capable of not, indeed he has learned and interacted or socialized. Social relationships are relationships between human beings and societies. Therefore, one of the goals that education should is to develop life skills. Education is a tool that is believed to be able to enhance a person's intelligence and personality in order to be better. The student's tough and optimistic personality is one of the key factors in facing life's challenges, both in personal, social and academic terms. However, the problem arises when education is too focused on the development of intellectuality without paying attention to the formation of character and values in the pupils. As a result, we can see moral degradation or moral destruction that ultimately leads to a violation of social values in social life [2].

Nowadays, there are many problems emerging in the world of education. For example, teenage sexual abuse, bribes, courageous opposition to school teachers and drug abuse. All these problems are serious challenges to be faced in education. If these problems are not addressed, they can have a negative impact on students' thinking patterns, attitudes, character, and behavior in schools, families, and society in general. What's more, in school and adolescence, individuals are undergoing a stage of development that seeks self-identity, wants attention, and is experiencing a transition to maturity. Therefore, it is crucial to find the right solutions to solve these problems [3].

In this article, the author will explore the role of educational sociology in strengthening student character. The author will explain what is Educational Sociology, Character Education,

Education Management as well as the Application of Educational Management based on the Sociology of Education for Student Characters Strengthening. The writer hopes this study will provide new insights and a better understanding of how education can act as an effective means of strengthening students' character.

Research Methods

This method of research uses qualitative study of literature, which is a method of gathering data by understanding and studying theories from various literature related to research. According to Sarwono [4], library research is the study of reference books and similar previous research results carried out by others. The aim is to obtain a theoretical basis for the problem being studied. Data collection uses different methods of searching for sources and construction from various sources, including books, journals, and research that has been done. Library materials derived from various references should be critically analyzed and thoroughly analyzed to support suggestions and ideas.

Results and Discussion

A. Sociology of Education

Etymologically, "sociology of education" comes from the words 'sociology' and 'education'. Sociology comes from Latin and Greek, namely the word *socius* which means society and *logos* which means science. Thus, the term sociology can be interpreted as the science of society. Sociology is the study of the relationship between humans in groups and their social structure. Experts also argue, one of them Nasution who states that the sociology of education is the study of ways to control the educational process to develop individual personalities for the better individual personality for the better. This definition wants education as a social activity in order to produce a generation that has a good personality, character and morals. In addition, there is also Abdullah who defines the sociology of education as a science that describes and explains institutions, social groups, social processes, where there is a social relationship with social interaction that individuals gain and organize their experiences.

Humans are social creatures who always work in groups and need each other. Sociology of education research emphasizes the social significance and results of education, and considers educational problems from the point of view of society as a whole, including social, political, economic and cultural aspects. Judging from the object of research, the sociology of education belongs to the group of social sciences, and in particular sociology and educational sciences in general belong to the group of social sciences. The social sciences now include economics, law, education, psychology, anthropology, and sociology. From here the position of sociology and pedagogy becomes clear.

The field of sociology that is directly related to education can be divided into two fields. Namely, (1) Education and society and (2) Education and social change [5]. From the point of view of society as a whole, the mission of education is to preserve culture. Culture is related to belief values, norms passed down from generation to generation that are always changing [6]. Schools and communities influence each other in many ways. Society being an agent in social change has several impacts of change, namely:

1. Technological Change

From a school perspective, technological change has two important impacts. Technological change is the potential for individuals to acquire new skills and technological change requires schools

to prepare their graduates to adapt to developments. Education in schools relies heavily on the use of learning media, communication tools, transformation and the biotechnology revolution.

2. Demographic Changes

Changes that occur related to the number, distribution and composition of the population. Their impact on education includes the development of educational policies, strict restrictions on admissions, imbalance between population growth and educational facilities, and urbanization and suburbanization. The mission of schools is to help diverse groups, mostly urban residents, adapt. Schools play an important role in supporting social control mechanisms in society, and they define the educational experience, especially in adequately preparing students for urban life.

3. Political changes in society, nation and state

Two major changes are occurring and will continue to occur, affecting education and taking place in the structure of the state and society. These are the increasing involvement of government in the activities of community members and the growing interdependence between state governments and other governments. Not only within communities but also between nations.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that sociology plays a very important role in education. Because sociology studies and regulates human relationships, both individuals with individuals, individuals with society, and even the government. Relationships with other people are also an important element in education. In fact, the emergence of sociology as a new scientific discipline led to the emergence of sociological theories and even the emergence of sociological theories that specifically focus on educational issues. This theory is known as the sociological theory of education.

B. Character Education

The definition of character according to the Ministry of Education Language Center is "innate, heart, soul, personality, character, behavior, personality, nature, character, disposition". As for having character is having personality, behavior, nature, character, and character". According to Tadkiroatun Musfiroh [2] research on education in influencing character, character refers to a series of attitudes, behaviors, motivations and skills. Character comes from the Greek word which means "to mark" or mark and focuses on how to apply good values in the form of actions or behavior so that people who are dishonest, cruel, greedy and other bad behaviors are said to be people with bad character. Conversely, people whose behavior is in accordance with the norms prevailing in society are said to be people with good character [7].

Efforts to instill character education through in Indonesia through the Character Education Enhancement (PPK) movement. Then it is emphasized with the idea of the Pancasila Student Profile which is in accordance with the Vision and Mission of the Ministry of Education and Culture as stated in the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 22 of 2020 concerning the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Education and Culture for 2020-2024. Through this PPK, the character of students can be formed more perfectly, strengthened through harmonization of heart (ethics), taste (aesthetics), mind (literacy) and exercise (kinesthetic); with the support of community involvement and cooperation between schools, families and communities. The character values instilled through the PPK movement are religious values, nationalism, independence, mutual cooperation and integrity. The urgency of PPK is to build human resources that are the foundation of the nation's development. The generation that must be raised is the Golden Generation, which has character quality, basic literacy and 4C skills (Critical thinking, Creativity, Communication, and Collaboration) [7].

Character education is a must because education does not only make students smart, education is also to build character and manners in life. Character is an important thing that a nation must have

to be able to exist in global competition. The structure of society in a country functions to maintain the character values that prevail in society so that people's lives are stable and orderly [8]. Character education teaches habits of thought and behavior that help individuals to live and work together as families, communities, and nations and helps them to make accountable decisions.

C. Education Management

Education management is a series of processes that continue to be carried out by educational institutions through the functionalization of management elements, where there are efforts to influence each other, direct each other, and monitor each other to achieve the overall goals of the educational organization. Education management includes organizing education related to all educational material needs related to all aspects involved in the implementation of education, which is directly related to the learning process, facilities, educational facilities and infrastructure, and educational media.

Education management as a science has different characteristics from other management sciences. The difference between education management and other management lies in its operational principles, not in general principles. Thus, although an understanding of general management principles is necessary to understand education management, it does not mean that knowledge of other management can be applied in education management because of its different operational principles [9].

In education management, there are activities that unite educational resources by focusing on predetermined targets. In the implementation process, there is cooperation, division of tasks and responsibilities, and different authorities. The management of educational institutions are related parts, such as teachers who are related to students. Teachers and learners are related to learning methods and materials, and so on without any separation so that goals can be achieved in an efficient and effective way. Education management can be interpreted as devotion or service to the world of education, because in his time management was imposed on jobs that had to do with devotion in the organization of education.

D. Implementation of Education Management Based on Sociology of Education for Strengthening Learners' Character

Education is not only about the acquisition of academic knowledge, but also about the formation of strong character and personality in students. Education based on sociology-based education understands that social factors in the educational environment can influence character growth in students. Therefore, the implementation of educational management based on the sociology of education is crucial to strengthen students' overall character. According to [6] there are three implications of education management based on the sociology of education in strengthening character.

The first is to make schools the first culture in character building. This is intended as a pattern that is tried to be developed in schools, so that schools can shape student character with the help of social institutions in instilling certain values in students. This can be done by creating a supportive, inclusive and safe school atmosphere for students. In addition, the integration of character values in the curriculum is very important. In this case, each subject should include learning about integrity, responsibility, cooperation, and tolerance.

Next, strengthen the relationship between character education and a community of character. In this case, schools must involve the community in student character building activities. This relationship needs to be created appropriately and carefully because in the community students will gain additional knowledge. Cooperation between schools and educational institutions, families,

communities, and other external partners can provide opportunities for students to face hands-on learning as well as direct involvement in social activities that are useful for strengthening student character.

Finally, making the sociology of education as a shaper of student character. This is because sociology has a role in shaping character in the world of education, namely by including character education in the learning process. At this time, character education has been implemented into the core competencies of each subject in the curriculum. These core competencies include practicing religious teachings, behaving honestly, discipline, responsibility, and also students are also taught to show attitudes as part of the solution to various problems in interacting efficiently in the social sphere and natural environment, while reflecting our nationality in the international world.

In addition, sociology of education has an important role in character building through application, implementation, analysis of social change, and focuses on strategies in creating harmonious relationships. In learning sociology, teachers also create various teaching materials that can strengthen student character. This learning material aims to be able to broaden views on and how to appreciate cultural differences, strengthen religious values, and improve self-adjustment to social change. The target of this learning material is for students to achieve skills and knowledge that lead to positive character strengthening.

Conclusion

Based on the research described in the discussion above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Sociology plays a very important role in education. Because sociology studies and regulates human relationships, both individuals with individuals, individuals with society, and even the government. Relationships with other people are also an important element in education.
2. Sociology of Education as a shaper of human character has a goal to develop the potential of students and grow into people with good hearts, good thoughts, and good actions, forming and training individual abilities continuously for self-improvement towards a better life, improving the quality of implementation and results of education in schools that lead to the achievement of character building and noble character of students as a whole, integrated, and balanced and strengthen and build real action in society.
3. The purpose of the sociology of education as a shaper of human character with integrity involves understanding and analyzing how the educational process contributes to:
 - a. The formation of individual character and moral values
 - b. Studying social interactions in the context of education
 - c. Analyzing the influence of the educational environment
 - c. Investigating the role of educators and the education system
 - d. Analyze the impact of values and norms in education
 - f. Assess the role of religion and ethics in education
 - e. Design educational strategies that promote integrity
4. The implementation of character with integrity is the result of the interaction between implementation strategies, program structure, educational goals, and positive directions. Therefore, optimizing the implementation of the sociology of education in character development through disciplinary habits requires strategic efforts to align educational stakeholders, especially teachers and principals in a culture of discipline. Cultivating discipline can be defined as embedding disciplinary habits into the school culture that reflects the values, norms, and common beliefs of all school members, including students, teachers, principals, and other education personnel.

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